

GHRITA KALPANAS IN NETRA ROGAS: A COMPREHENSIVE AYURVEDIC REVIEW

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Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 05 Jan. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18153056>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Shabnam Verma^{1*}
(BAMS), Prof. Dr. Vijayant Bhardwaj² (BAMS,
MS) Dr. Hardev Singh Thakur³ (BAMS, MS),
Dr. Shiwani Chauhan⁴ (BAMS, MS) (2026).
GHRITA KALPANAS IN NETRA ROGAS: A
COMPREHENSIVE AYURVEDIC REVIEW.
"World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research,
15(1), 1498-1505.

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda considers the eye (*Netra*) as the most important sense organ, and its protection is given prime importance in classical texts. Among various therapeutic modalities described for *Netra Rogas*, *Ghrita Kalpanas* occupy a pivotal role due to their *Chakshushya*, *Rasayana*, *Brihana*, and *Doṣha Shamaka* properties. *Ghrita* acts as an ideal drug carrier, facilitating deeper tissue penetration and enhanced bioavailability. Classical Ayurvedic *Samhitas* such as *Sushruta Samhita*, *Charaka Samhita*, *Aṣṭāṅga Hridaya*, *Aṣṭāṅga Sangraha*, *Sharngadhara Samhita*, and *Chakradatta* describe numerous *Ghrita* formulations specifically indicated for *Netra Rogas*. This article systematically reviews all *Ghrita Kalpanas* mentioned in various classical texts for ocular disorders.

KEYWORDS: *Ghrita Kalpana*, *Netra Roga*, *Chakshushya*, *Shalaky Tantra*, *Rasayana*.

INTRODUCTION

The eye is regarded as the foremost among all sense organs in Ayurveda.

“सर्वेन्द्रियाणां नयनं प्रधानम्

तस्माद् विशेषेण परिरक्षणीयम्॥”^[1] (Su. Sa. Ut. 1/3)

Shalaky Tantra, one of the eight branches of *Aṣṭāṅga Ayurveda*, deals with diseases of *Urdhva Jatrugata Sthana*. The first nineteen chapters of *Sushruta Samhita Uttarantra* are exclusively devoted to *Netra Rogas*, emphasizing the importance of ocular health.

Importance of *Ghrita* in *Netra Rogas*

Ghrita is considered the best among *Sneha Dravyas* due to its ability to assimilate the properties of drugs processed with it.

“संस्कारस्य अनुवर्तनाद् घृतं गुणवत्तरं स्मृतम्।

तस्मात् सर्वेषु स्नेहेषु घृतमेव विशिष्यते॥”^[2] (Ch. Sa. Su. 13/13)

Ghrita is *Madhura Rasa*, *Shita Virya*, *Snigdha*, *Mridu*, and *Sukshma*, making it especially beneficial for diseases of the eye dominated by *Vata* and *Pitta*.

“घृतं चक्षुष्यं मेध्यं बल्यं वातपित्तहरं परम्।

रसायनं च सर्वेषां स्नेहेषु प्रविशिष्यते॥”^[3] (Aṣ. Hr. Su. 5/37)

Ghrita Kalpanas Mentioned in Various *Samhitas* for *Netra Rogas*

I. *Ghrita Kalpanas* in *Sushruta Samhita*

1. *Jivantyadi Ghrita*^[4]

जीवन्ती मधुकं द्राक्षां काकोल्यादिगणं तथा।

क्षीरं च घृतसंयुक्तं पचेत् नेत्रामयान् जयेत्॥

पित्ताभिष्यन्ददाहेषु रक्तजानां च नाशनम्।

चक्षुष्यं बल्यं मेध्यं जीवन्त्यादि घृतं स्मृतम्॥ (Su. Sa. Ut. 7/12–14)

Indications: *Pittaja Netra Roga, Daha, Raga, Pittaj Abhishyanda*

Aspect	Action
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Pitta-Rakta Shaman</i>
<i>Guna</i>	<i>Snighdha, Shita</i>
<i>Karma</i>	<i>Chakshushya, Balyam, Medhya, Rasayana</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Ras and Rakta Pushti</i>
Clinical effect	Reduces <i>Daha, Raga, Shopha</i> , improves vision

2. *Triphala Ghrita*^[5]

त्रिफलां पाययेद् घृतं तिमिरकाचपटलापहम्।

चक्षुष्यं बल्यं मेध्यं नेत्ररोगनिवारणम्॥ (Su. Sa. Ut. 9/25–27)

Indications: *Timira, Kacha, Patala, Abhishyanda*

Aspect	Action
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Tridosha Shaman (Pitta-Kapha dominant)</i>
<i>Karam</i>	<i>Chakshushya, Balya, Medhya, Rasayana</i>
<i>Disease</i>	<i>Timir, Kacha, Patalagat Rogas</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Ras-Rakta Pushti</i>
Special property	<i>Yogvahi, Sukshma</i>

3. *Drakshadi Ghrita*^[6]

द्राक्षां मधुकं क्षीरं घृतेन सह साधयेत्।

पित्तदाहेषु रक्तेषु नेत्ररोगेषु शस्यते॥ (Su. Sa. Ut. 10/8–10)

Indications: *Raktaja and Pittaja Netra Rogas*

Aspect	Action
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Pitta-Rakta Shaman</i>
<i>Guna</i>	<i>Sheeta, Snigadha, Yogavahi</i>
<i>Karam</i>	<i>Daha Prashaman, Chakshushya</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rasa-Rakta Pushti</i>
Indications	<i>Pitta Raktaj Netra Rogas</i>

II. *Ghrita Kalpanas in Charaka Samhita*

Though Charaka focuses mainly on systemic therapy, several *Ghritas* beneficial for vision are mentioned.

4. *Triphala Ghrita*^[7] (*Chakṣuṣya Rasayana*)

त्रिफलाघृतमशनीयान्नित्यं मेध्यमनुत्तमम्।

चक्षुष्यं दीर्घमायुष्यं वलीपलितनाशनम्॥ (Ch. Sa. Chi. 1/2/17–18)

Aspect	Action
Primary <i>Karam</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>
<i>Dosha Action</i>	<i>Tridosh Shaman</i>
Ocular effect	<i>Chakshushya</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rasa-Rakta Pushti</i>
Special property	<i>Medhya, Yogavahi</i>
Clinical utility	Preventive and promotive in <i>Netra Rogas</i>

5. Mahatiktaka Ghrita^[8]

महातिक्तकं घृतं पित्तकुष्ठविसर्पनुत्।

रक्तदोषहरं चैव दाहशोफप्रणाशनम्॥ (Ch. Sa. Chi. 7/144–147)

Aspect	Action
<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Tikta</i>
<i>Dosha action</i>	<i>Pitta-Rakta Shaman</i>
<i>Mukhya Karam</i>	<i>Daha, Shopha Prashaman, Kushtha, Visarpanut</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rakta Prasadana</i>
Clinical Utility	Inflammatory <i>Netra Rogas</i>
Special Properties	<i>Yogvahi, Srotoshodhan</i>

Indications: Pitta–Raktaja disorders including ocular inflammations.

III. Ghrita Kalpanas in Aṣṭāṅga Hridaya

6. Triphala Ghrita^[9]

त्रिफलाघृतमशनीयात्तिमिरकाचापहम्।

चक्षुष्यं बल्यं मेध्यं नेत्ररोगनिवारणम्॥ (Aṣ. Hr. Ut. 13/29–31)

Aspect	Action
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Tridosha Shaman</i>
Disease	<i>Timir, Kacha</i>
<i>Karam</i>	<i>Chakshushya, Medhya</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rasa-Rakta Pushti</i>
Special Qualities	<i>Balya, Medhya, Yogvahi</i>

Indications: Timira, Kacha, Netra Daurbalya

7. Mahatriphala Ghrita^[10]

महात्रिफलया सिद्धं घृतं तिमिरकाचापहम्।

पटलानां विनाशायचक्षुष्यं बलवर्धनम्॥ (Aṣ. Hr. Ut. 13/32–35)

Aspect	Action
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Tridosha Shaman</i>
Disease	<i>Timir, Kacha, Patala</i>
<i>Karam</i>	<i>Chakshushya, Rasayana</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rasa-Rakta-Majja Pushti</i>
Special Effect	<i>Balaya, Vrihana</i>
Clinical Use	Chronic and degenerative Netra Rogas

Indications: Chronic *Netra Rogas*, vision impairment

8. Patoladi Ghrita^[11]

पाटोलं निम्बनिम्बार्कत्रिफलां मधुकं तथा।

साधयेद् घृतसंयुक्तं पित्ताभिष्यन्दनाशनम्॥ (Aṣ. Hr. Ut. 10/15–17)

Aspect	Action
<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Tikta</i>
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Pitta-Rakta Shaman</i>
Primary Action	<i>Abhishyand Nashan</i>
Associated Effects	<i>Daha, Raga, Shopha Prashaman</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rakta Prasadana</i>
Special Property	<i>Yogvahi, Srotoshodhana</i>

Indications: *Abhishyanda*, inflammatory eye diseases

IV. Ghrita Kalpanas in Aṣṭanga Sangraha

9. Jivantyadi Ghrita^[12]

जीवन्ती मधुकं द्राक्षांपयस्यां च समांशिकाम्।

साधयेद् घृतसंयुक्तां सर्वनेत्रामयापहाम्॥ (Aṣ. Sa. Ut. 16/20–22)

Aspect	Action
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Tridosha Shamana (Vata-Pitta Dominant)</i>
<i>Karma</i>	<i>Chakshushya, Rasayan, Vrihana</i>
Disease	<i>Sarva Netra Rogas</i>
<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Rasa-Rakta-Majja Pushti</i>
Special Property	<i>Yogvahi, Jivaniya</i>

Indications: *Pittaja Netra Rogas*

V. Ghrita Kalpanas in Sharangadhara Samhita

10. Triphala Ghrita^[13]

त्रिफलां साधयेद् घृतेचक्षुष्यं तिमिरापहम्।

मेध्यं बल्यं रसायनदोषघ्नं दीपनं परम्॥ (Sha. Sa. Madhyam Khanda 9/15–17)

Aspect	Action
Primary Karam	<i>Chakshushya, Timir Nashan</i>
Dosha	<i>Tridosha Shaman</i>
Dhatu	<i>Rasa-Rakta-Majja Pushti</i>
Special Effects	<i>Rasayana, Balaya, Medhya</i>
Clinical Utility	<i>Visual debility, Timira, Chronic Netra Roga</i>

Indications: *Chakṣuṣya, Rasayana*

VI. Ghrita Kalpanas in Chakradutta

11. Mahatriphala Ghrita^[14]

महात्रिफलया सिद्धं घृतं तिमिरकाचापहम्।

चक्षुष्यं पटलघ्नं च सर्वनेत्रामयापहम्॥ (Chakradutta, Netra Roga Chikitsa 76/25–28)

Aspect	Action
Primary Karam	<i>Timir kacha nashanam</i>
Special Action	<i>Patalghan</i>
Dosha	<i>Tridosh Shaman</i>
Dhatu	<i>Rasa-Rakta-Majja Pushti</i>
Special property	<i>Chakshushya, Rasayana</i>
Clinical Utility	<i>Chronic and Degenerative Netra Roga</i>

Indications: *Timira, Kacha, Linganasa*

Use of Ghrita in Netra Kriya Kalpa

Ghritas are extensively used in:

- *Tarpana*
- *Putapaka*
- *Aschyotana*

“तर्पणं चक्षुष्यं प्रोक्तं बलवर्धनमेव च।

नेत्ररोगप्रशमनं दृष्टेः स्थैर्यकरं परम्॥”^[15] (Su. Sa. Ut. 18/15–17)

Probable Mode of Action

- *Snigdha and Brihana* properties counteract *Vata*-induced dryness
- *Sheeta Virya* pacifies *Pitta* and *Raktaja* inflammation
- *Ghrita* enhances drug penetration (*Sukṣma Guna*)

- Acts as a nourishing agent for ocular tissues (*Dhatu Puṣṭi*)

CONCLUSION

Ghrita Kalpanas play a crucial role in the prevention and management of *Netra Rogas* as described in classical Ayurvedic texts. Their multidimensional actions—*Chakṣhuṣya*, *Rasayana*, *Doṣha Shamaka*, and *Bṛihaṇa*—make them indispensable in ophthalmic practice. The extensive references across all major *Samhitas* validate their therapeutic importance. Proper selection and application of *Ghrita Kalpanas*, along with appropriate *Pathya*–*Apathya*, can significantly help in preserving vision and preventing ocular disorders in the present era.

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